

MODELLING OF FLOW PROCESSES DURING
THERMOFORMING OF CONTINUOUS CF/PP-LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

One of the main advantages using thermoplastic polymers as matrices for continuous fibre reinforced composites is their feature to melt under heat and pressure. Using preimpregnated, unidirectionally reinforced tape material for the lay-up, a laminate can be described as an alternating sequence of fibre rich layers and thin resin interlayers. During a thermoforming process, e.g. over a single curvature tool, the fibre rich layers must slip relative to each other, in order to reach the new, desired shape without fibre breakage or wrinkling effects. To characterize the effect of ply orientation on this flow process, laminates with differently oriented plies were thermoformed under isothermal condition into a 90°-bend. Finite Element Analysis helps to illustrate the observed tendency that the slip is eased if the plies are oriented transverse to slip direction. Experimental work, where the resin interlayers were subjected to a shear traction, underlines the tendency that adjacent plies slip easier onto each other if they are oriented non-parallel.

KEY WORDS: Flow Processes; Thermoforming; Finite Element Analysis;
Stacking Sequence; Thermoplastic Composite

1. INTRODUCTION

The main feature of a thermoforming process of continuous fibre-reinforced thermoplastics is the fluid state of the matrix material when being heated above its melting temperature. For the production of thermoplastic composite components, one possibility is to use preimpregnated layers, which are laid-up in a flat mould and consolidated under heat and pressure to a laminated sheet. This sheet deals as an intermediate and can be reheated whenever being thermoformed, for example by press-forming techniques, into the final shape.

Several flow processes of the fibres and the polymer, which are present in a thermoforming process, have been classified in the literature [1-3]. The interply-slip process is desired because otherwise an initially flat laminate cannot be formed satisfactorily to a single-curvature part. In two-dimensional thermoforming experiments, isothermal conditions were chosen to guarantee an uniform temperature of the laminate during forming. The two matching dies and the laminate were heated in a heatable chamber by circulating air, and for cooling the part, the oven was opened, and the laminate was cooled down below its melting point to be removed from the tool (Figure 1, left). This slippage mainly took place in the resin interlayers, which can be seen in a cross-section of the bend region of a thermoformed Carbon Fibre/Polypropylene (CF/PP)-laminate (Figure 1, right). In this unsymmetric lay-up, the plies were oriented in such a way that no adjacent plies were parallel, except of the outer 0° -layers. This recommendation was a result of so-called ply-pull-out experiments, where the resin interlayers were subjected to a shear load and their resistance to shear was measured depending on lay-up, slip velocity, temperature and pressure [4].

2. FINITE ELEMENT SIMULATION OF THE INTERPLY-SLIP FLOW PROCESS

A microscopic section of the resin interlayer should help to obtain a more fundamental understanding of the influence of lay-up on the resistance versus slip (Figure 2a). Only one half of the interlayer is modelled for symmetry reasons, and is sufficient to study the material behaviour under shear load (Figure 2b). Here, 20-noded, isoparametric three-dimensional brick elements have been chosen to model a section of the fibre rich layer and resin interlayer [5]. For the mesh generation, the pre-processing capabilities of MENTAT were helpful. Symmetry conditions were used to reduce the number of finite elements. The backside is constrained to remain fixed by suppressing the movement of all nodes (3 translational degrees of freedom, x, y, and z direction). On the front, all nodes were allowed to move freely in the xz-plane, but no nodal displacement was allowed in y-direction. A typical fibre diameter of $8\ \mu\text{m}$ was assumed and the total thickness in y-direction amounts to $15\ \mu\text{m}$. A plastic-viscoelastic (viscoplastic) material model has to be defined for the polymeric matrix, and the fibres were assumed to be elastic. The material model of the matrix was found for the interply-slip process and the transverse flow behaviour [4,6,7]. As the material properties of the fibres only slightly decrease at thermoforming temperature, elastic values at room temperature were taken. The resistance against deformation was compared, either in fibre (z-direction) or in transverse direction (x-direction). Equal displacement increments were defined to model a constant velocity of all nodes on the back side, either in x- or z-direction.

In such a model, a three-dimensional stress situation is present, and the von-Mises yield criterion was appropriate to determine the beginning of plastic deformation behaviour of the polymeric material. To compare the material behaviour due to different shear traction along and perpendicular to fibre direction, only the shear stress components were selected, which are part

of the total stress state in the matrix. Therefore, the finite elements which were defined for modelling the fibres, are not plotted in the following contour plots.

In Figure 2b, the shear stresses in xz -plane are plotted, for the case that all nodes on the backside of the mesh have a total displacement of 0.1mm in positive x -direction. The nodal displacements in this direction are represented by the deformed mesh. The stresses are referred to a yield shear stress to demonstrate the increase of plastified areas in the matrix. Here, the effect of the fibres is obvious. Due to the reduction of the interlayer height (y -direction), the shear stresses increase where the fibres are present. Regarding the shear stress distribution perpendicular to the fibres (from nodes A to B), these stresses are maximum in the fibre area. Additionally, one can regard the high shear stresses concentration along the fibres as a shear traction on the interface between fibre and matrix. As the matrix is in the molten state, the matrix behaves viscoplastically and the resistance versus deformation decreases once the yield level has been reached. Only a small increase of applied stress is sufficient to ease matrix deformation. In this model, ideal bonding between fibre and matrix was assumed.

By comparing the shear stresses, now in xy -plane, which are built-up due to the displacement of the backside in x -direction (perpendicular to the fibres) at the same deformation step, they increase according to the reduction of the interlayer height (Figure 2c). Considering the maximum values, the resistance against shear deformation is slightly higher by moving the backside perpendicular to the fibres.

At displacement increment 5, nearly the same shear stress distribution in xz -plane was calculated as for the first increment, but because of the higher deformation state, the stress level has increased (Figure 3a, in comparison to Figure 2b). In the areas where the fibres exist, yielding takes place. In between the fibres, the stresses are increasing, and the area of yield increases from the fibre interface in the middle of the fibres (light colours) to the area in between the fibres. The dark area indicates that the matrix has not been deformed to the same extent as the other areas.

In Figure 3b, where the movement in x -direction is continued, this area is more affected. The whole matrix on top of the fibres has a nearly uniform stress distribution, and therefore it will tend to be deformed more easily. The maximum values are less, compared to the movement in fibre direction (Figure 3a), because the material is deformed more homogeneously.

Concerning the shear stress distribution in xz -plane for increment 11 (Figure 4a), the yield shear stress has been exceeded in between the fibres. Still, there exist areas of lower stress states (dark areas). In contrast, all matrix elements, except some elements at the sides, show that the yield level has been reached when the main movement is transverse to fibre direction (Figure 4b). The comparison between these two stress contours, both for the same level of shear deformation, leads to following conclusions: On the one hand side, the resistance against shear deformation is initially easier for the movement parallel to fibre direction (Figures 2b, in comparison to Figure 2c). On the other side, the matrix flow is hindered by the fibres when the backside moves in transverse direction. This leads to an increase of stresses, and consequently the yield level is reached earlier for this case. The matrix shows a more homogeneous stress

distribution in the resin interlayer (Figure 3b). For the movement parallel to the fibres, only the stress values are higher, but no change in distribution is obvious (Figure 3a). Thus, overall yielding of the matrix earlier for the movement in transverse direction, compared to the stress state parallel to the fibres (Figures 4a and 4b). Overall yielding for the movement in fibre direction was calculated at a later deformation step (Increment 15, which is not plotted here). The development of shear stresses with time (Node A) is plotted in Figure 5. The displacement increments, on the x-axis, are the same as shown on the contour plots before. As this stationary level is reached earlier for the movement in transverse direction (90° to fibre direction), the stationary level is consequently less than the value found for the movement in fibre direction (0° -direction). Initially, the shear stresses increase more than for a higher level of deformation. Once a yield shear stress, which indicates the change of the material response against shear deformation, is exceeded, the stresses do only increase slightly and reach finally a stationary level. Additionally, the shear stress-increment curve of a model is included, where only matrix properties for all finite elements were defined. The deformation resistance of such a neat, unreinforced polymer block is less than in the reinforced models. This underlines the conclusion that the reduction of interlayer height through the presence of fibres leads to an increase to interply-slip.

3. EXPERIMENTAL VERIFICATION

The results from the Finite Element calculations were compared to those obtained by experimental work. First, a steel foil, which was placed in the middle of a lay-up, was pulled-out of a laminate under thermoforming conditions. The two adjacent prepreg layers, one on each side of this steel foil, were either 0° , 45° or 90° -oriented. The shear stress in the resin interlayer was measured depending on lay-up and slip velocity. It was found that the steel foil slips easier relative to a 90° -ply, compared to a 0° -ply. The shear force-displacement curves of furthergoing pull-out experiments, where the resin interlayer in between differently oriented plies was subjected to shear, are shown in Figure 6.

Secondly, initially flat PP/CF-laminates were thermoformed into a 90° -angle in a matched-die forming process (Figure 1, left). The tips of the laminates were investigated, mainly considering the interply-slip process. A $0^\circ/0^\circ$ -combination slipped more difficult than a $0^\circ/90^\circ$ -combination. Additionally, the slip of a $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ -combination is easier than a $+45^\circ/+45^\circ$ -combination. The more the plies are oriented non-parallel to each other, the easier the interply-slip process occurred. This is in good agreement with the modelling studies as the slip is easier transverse to the fibre direction.

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The presented Finite Element Simulation of the Interply-Slip flow process, here on a microscopic level, showed that the plies do slip easier if they are moved transverse to fibre direction. Initially, the slip in fibre direction is easier, but due to the visco-plastic material model for the polymer in its molten state, the resistance against a shear traction decreases for a higher level of deformation. Therefore, the $0^\circ/0^\circ$, $45^\circ/45^\circ$ and $90^\circ/90^\circ$ -combinations slip more difficult than $0^\circ/90^\circ$ and $+45^\circ/-45^\circ$ -combinations. In order to guarantee an easy slip, the plies of a laminate have to be oriented so that, even in more complex, three-dimensional geometries, these rules will have to be followed.

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7. BIOGRAPHY

Roger Scherer has passed his Diploma Degree in Mechanical Engineering at the Technical University Hamburg-Harburg in April 1989. The Diploma Thesis, in the field of thermoplastic composites, was based on the work done during a half-year internship at the ICI Wilton Materials Research Centre, UK. Since May 1989, he works as PhD student under the supervision of Professor Klaus Friedrich.

Figure 1 Matched-Die Thermoforming Experiments under Isothermal Conditions: The laminate length was adapted to the tool geometry so that it was only bent in the centre of the tool after forming (left); A indicates one of the resin interlayers (right)

Figure 2a Microscopic Section through a Layered Thermoplastic Composite; The laminate is build-up of alternating fibre rich layers and resin interlayers

Figure 2b Increment 1, Shear Stress Distribution in xz-Plane
Backside movement in z-direction (parallel to fibre direction)

Figure 2c Increment 1, Shear Stress Distribution in xy-Plane
Backside movement in x-direction (transverse to fibre direction)

Figure 3a Increment 5, Shear Stress Distribution in xz-Plane
Backside movement in z-direction (parallel to fibre direction)

Figure 3b Increment 5, Shear Stress Distribution in xy-Plane
Backside movement in x-direction (transverse to fibre direction)

Figure 4a Increment 11, Shear Stress Distribution in xz-Plane
Backside movement in z-direction (parallel to fibre direction)

Figure 4b Increment 11, Shear Stress Distribution in xy-Plane
Backside movement in x-direction (transverse to fibre direction)

Figure 5 Shear Stress-Displacement Curves for Different Combinations

Figure 6 Ply-Pull-Out Experiment; The resistance (Force F) against a shear deformation of the resin interlayers at different layers velocities (v) was measured depending on the lay-up of the adjacent fibre rich layers